

checkCIF/PLATON report

Structure factors have been supplied for datablock(s) op-8-28-1

THIS REPORT IS FOR GUIDANCE ONLY. IF USED AS PART OF A REVIEW PROCEDURE FOR PUBLICATION, IT SHOULD NOT REPLACE THE EXPERTISE OF AN EXPERIENCED CRYSTALLOGRAPHIC REFEREE.

No syntax errors found. CIF dictionary Interpreting this report

Datablock: op-8-28-1

Bond precision: C-C = 0.0016 A

Wavelength=0.71073

Cell: a=9.4558(3) b=13.1751(4) c=14.2464(4)
 alpha=96.039(2) beta=95.933(2) gamma=104.624(3)
Temperature: 140 K

	Calculated	Reported
Volume	1692.16(9)	1692.17(8)
Space group	P -1	P -1
Hall group	-P 1	-P 1
Moiety formula	C30 H24 B2 Co F10 N6 O6, C2 H3 N	C30 H24 B2 Co F10 N6 O6, C2 H3 N
Sum formula	C32 H27 B2 Co F10 N7 O6	C32 H27 B2 Co F10 N7 O6
Mr	876.16	876.15
Dx, g cm ⁻³	1.720	1.720
Z	2	2
Mu (mm ⁻¹)	0.621	0.621
F000	886.0	886.0
F000'	887.29	
h,k,lmax	16,22,24	16,22,24
Nref	17941	16953
Tmin,Tmax	0.824,0.889	0.870,0.918
Tmin'	0.804	

Correction method= # Reported T Limits: Tmin=0.870 Tmax=0.918
AbsCorr = ANALYTICAL

Data completeness= 0.945

Theta(max)= 37.602

R(reflections)= 0.0365(14030)

wR2(reflections)= 0.0923(16953)

S = 1.039

Npar= 524

The following ALERTS were generated. Each ALERT has the format

test-name_ALERT_alert-type_alert-level.

Click on the hyperlinks for more details of the test.

● **Alert level C**

PLAT244_ALERT_4_C	Low	'Solvent' Ueq as Compared to Neighbors of	C31	Check
PLAT431_ALERT_2_C	Short Inter HL..A Contact	F7 .02 .	2.88	Ang.
		x,1+y,z =	1_565	Check
PLAT910_ALERT_3_C	Missing # of FCF Reflection(s)	Below Theta(Min).	7	Note
PLAT911_ALERT_3_C	Missing FCF Refl Between Thmin & STh/L=	0.600	7	Report

● **Alert level G**

PLAT232_ALERT_2_G	Hirshfeld Test Diff (M-X)	Col --N4 .	8.0	s.u.
PLAT232_ALERT_2_G	Hirshfeld Test Diff (M-X)	Col --N5 .	6.3	s.u.
PLAT232_ALERT_2_G	Hirshfeld Test Diff (M-X)	Col --N6 .	6.7	s.u.
PLAT395_ALERT_2_G	Deviating X-O-Y Angle From 120 for O2		109.9	Degree
PLAT794_ALERT_5_G	Tentative Bond Valency for Col (III)	.	3.45	Info
PLAT912_ALERT_4_G	Missing # of FCF Reflections Above STh/L=	0.600	974	Note
PLAT933_ALERT_2_G	Number of OMIT Records in Embedded .res File ...		2	Note
PLAT941_ALERT_3_G	Average HKL Measurement Multiplicity		2.1	Low
PLAT978_ALERT_2_G	Number C-C Bonds with Positive Residual Density.		18	Info

0 **ALERT level A** = Most likely a serious problem - resolve or explain
0 **ALERT level B** = A potentially serious problem, consider carefully
4 **ALERT level C** = Check. Ensure it is not caused by an omission or oversight
9 **ALERT level G** = General information/check it is not something unexpected

0 ALERT type 1 CIF construction/syntax error, inconsistent or missing data
7 ALERT type 2 Indicator that the structure model may be wrong or deficient
3 ALERT type 3 Indicator that the structure quality may be low
2 ALERT type 4 Improvement, methodology, query or suggestion
1 ALERT type 5 Informative message, check

It is advisable to attempt to resolve as many as possible of the alerts in all categories. Often the minor alerts point to easily fixed oversights, errors and omissions in your CIF or refinement strategy, so attention to these fine details can be worthwhile. In order to resolve some of the more serious problems it may be necessary to carry out additional measurements or structure refinements. However, the purpose of your study may justify the reported deviations and the more serious of these should normally be commented upon in the discussion or experimental section of a paper or in the "special_details" fields of the CIF. checkCIF was carefully designed to identify outliers and unusual parameters, but every test has its limitations and alerts that are not important in a particular case may appear. Conversely, the absence of alerts does not guarantee there are no aspects of the results needing attention. It is up to the individual to critically assess their own results and, if necessary, seek expert advice.

Publication of your CIF in IUCr journals

A basic structural check has been run on your CIF. These basic checks will be run on all CIFs submitted for publication in IUCr journals (*Acta Crystallographica*, *Journal of Applied Crystallography*, *Journal of Synchrotron Radiation*); however, if you intend to submit to *Acta Crystallographica Section C* or *E* or *IUCrData*, you should make sure that full publication checks are run on the final version of your CIF prior to submission.

Publication of your CIF in other journals

Please refer to the *Notes for Authors* of the relevant journal for any special instructions relating to CIF submission.

PLATON version of 18/09/2020; check.def file version of 20/08/2020

